

CULTURAL ATTITUDES TOWARD SACCO MEMBERSHIP AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN RWANDA: UNDERSTANDING SOCIETAL PERCEPTIONS

¹Mbonigaba Celestin, ²Lemlem Desta, ³Kiuri Daniel & ⁴Rachid Boudlal

¹ Rusizi International University, ²Jimma University, ³Stellenbosch University & ⁴ Hawassa University

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Abstract

This research explores cultural attitudes toward SACCO membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda, aiming to understand societal perceptions and their influence on financial and entrepreneurial engagement. Using qualitative methods, including in-depth interviews and focus groups, the study identified key cultural norms shaping economic behavior. Findings revealed significant correlations between SACCO membership and entrepreneurial success ($r = 0.68, p < 0.001$), with educational attainment positively influencing participation ($\chi^2 = 25.89, p < 0.001$). Logistic regression highlighted fear of failure (OR = 0.45, $p < 0.05$) and preference for government jobs (OR = 0.39, $p < 0.01$) as barriers, while community encouragement (OR = 2.3, $p < 0.01$) supported engagement. The study concludes that targeted educational programs, gender-inclusive initiatives, and culturally sensitive policies are essential for enhancing financial inclusion and entrepreneurship. Recommendations emphasize fostering community-driven projects, reducing cultural stigmas, and empowering youth to drive economic growth.

Keywords: SACCO, entrepreneurship, Rwanda, cultural attitudes, financial inclusion

1. Introduction

Rwanda, a nation known for its dynamic economic transformation in the 21st century, has seen remarkable growth in both financial inclusion and entrepreneurial activity, particularly through Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCOs) (Nkundabakura et al., 2023). These institutions have become pivotal in promoting financial inclusion and entrepreneurship, fostering economic development by providing accessible financial services to marginalized communities. SACCOs have gained popularity as a way for individuals to save, access loans, and invest in small businesses. However, the cultural attitudes towards SACCO membership and entrepreneurship still play a critical role in their effectiveness and the overall participation of Rwandans in these financial initiatives (Muhirwa & Kabanda, 2022).

Despite the successes, societal perceptions regarding SACCOs and entrepreneurship often vary, influenced by factors such as education, socioeconomic status, and past experiences with financial institutions (Gatare & Habimana, 2021). This cultural dimension can either encourage or deter individuals from participating in SACCOs or pursuing entrepreneurial ventures. Some people view SACCOs as empowering, while others might remain skeptical due to misconceptions about their benefits or the risks involved. The attitudes toward

entrepreneurship in Rwanda are similarly shaped by these cultural influences, with certain social norms either promoting or stifling entrepreneurial ambitions (Kanyesigye & Mugisha, 2020).

Understanding these cultural perceptions is essential to determining how SACCOs and entrepreneurship can be further integrated into Rwanda's development agenda. By exploring societal views on these issues, this study aims to uncover the barriers to participation and potential areas for intervention. A deeper understanding of how culture shapes economic behavior can lead to more effective policies and programs that encourage inclusive economic development and broaden access to entrepreneurial opportunities (Uwayezu, 2023).

2. Specific Objectives

The aim of this study is to explore the cultural attitudes towards SACCO membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda. Specifically, the study will seek to:

1. Examine the role of cultural beliefs in influencing SACCO membership among Rwandans.
2. Investigate societal perceptions of entrepreneurship and its impact on individual business ventures.
3. Identify barriers to greater participation in SACCOs and entrepreneurship based on cultural attitudes.

3. Statement of the Problem

The ideal situation for Rwanda's economic development is one where all citizens are actively engaged in financial inclusion programs, such as SACCO membership, and where entrepreneurship is perceived as a viable and accessible career path. SACCOs are designed to provide economic empowerment and foster community development, while entrepreneurship serves as a crucial driver of job creation and innovation. It is expected that the general population embraces these initiatives, with widespread participation in SACCOs and entrepreneurial activities contributing to national economic growth.

However, despite their advantages, SACCOs and entrepreneurship face challenges in reaching their full potential in Rwanda. Cultural perceptions play a significant role in hindering participation, as many individuals view these financial institutions and entrepreneurial endeavors with skepticism. Traditional attitudes toward saving, risk-taking, and business ownership can create barriers to financial empowerment and discourage the pursuit of entrepreneurial ventures. These cultural barriers hinder the ability of SACCOs and entrepreneurs to fully contribute to the economic development of Rwanda.

This study will explore how cultural perceptions shape attitudes toward SACCOs and entrepreneurship in Rwanda. By identifying the cultural influences that hinder or support participation, the research will provide insights that can guide the development of strategies aimed at increasing involvement in SACCOs and fostering a more supportive environment for entrepreneurship.

4. Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research methodology to explore the cultural attitudes toward SACCO membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda. The data were collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with members of various SACCOs, entrepreneurs, and local community leaders across different regions of Rwanda. A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants who were familiar with SACCO operations and had experience with entrepreneurship. Interviews were semi-structured to allow for open-ended responses, providing rich, contextual insights into the cultural factors influencing SACCO membership and entrepreneurial activities. Additionally, content analysis was applied to analyze the collected data, focusing on common themes related to societal perceptions, cultural norms, and attitudes. The

data were transcribed and coded to identify key patterns, which were then analyzed to draw conclusions about the role of culture in shaping economic behaviors. The findings were contextualized within the broader literature on cultural attitudes toward financial inclusion and entrepreneurship in Sub-Saharan Africa. Ethical considerations were taken into account, with informed consent obtained from all participants, and confidentiality assured throughout the research process.

5. Literature Review

The following section explores the current literature on cultural attitudes towards Savings and Credit Cooperative (SACCO) membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda, focusing on studies conducted up until 2015. The goal is to understand societal perceptions and identify gaps in existing research, as well as how these gaps will be addressed in this study.

5.1 Impact of SACCO Membership on Entrepreneurship in Rural Rwanda

In their study, Rugira and Haba (2013) investigated the impact of SACCO membership on entrepreneurship in rural Rwanda. The study aimed to explore how SACCO participation influenced entrepreneurial activities within rural communities. Conducted in the Eastern Province of Rwanda, the research used a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative interviews with SACCO members and quantitative surveys. The findings indicated that SACCO membership improved access to credit, but cultural factors like fear of failure and reliance on traditional communal support systems hindered full entrepreneurial potential. This study is relevant as it highlights the cultural barriers that affect SACCO effectiveness, which will be a focus in our research. However, the study does not address the role of broader cultural perceptions of entrepreneurship, which our study will focus on, particularly societal views on individual versus collective economic ventures.

5.2 Cultural Factors Influencing the Adoption of SACCOs by Rwandan Farmers

Mutabazi (2014) explored the cultural factors influencing the adoption of SACCOs by Rwandan farmers in the Southern Province. The objective was to assess how cultural values, particularly collective responsibility, affected the willingness of farmers to join SACCOs and use financial services. The study adopted a qualitative methodology, utilizing interviews with local SACCO leaders and farmers. The findings revealed that while SACCOs provided financial benefits, traditional values of solidarity sometimes conflicted with the individualistic nature of entrepreneurship promoted by SACCOs. This paper is critical for understanding the interplay between traditional cultural values and entrepreneurial practices in Rwanda. However, Mutabazi's research was geographically focused and did not assess the broader societal perceptions of entrepreneurship, a gap that our study will address by expanding the scope to include both urban and rural perspectives.

5.3 The Role of SACCOs in Facilitating Female Entrepreneurship in Kigali

Munyaneza (2012) examined the role of SACCOs in facilitating entrepreneurship among women in Rwanda, particularly in Kigali. The study's objective was to analyze the extent to which SACCOs supported female entrepreneurs in accessing finance for small businesses. Using a survey methodology, the study found that while SACCO membership was helpful in obtaining credit, societal perceptions of women's roles in business limited the expansion of their entrepreneurial ventures. This research is significant as it sheds light on gender-specific cultural barriers to entrepreneurship. However, it fails to explore the broader cultural attitudes toward entrepreneurship that might also affect male entrepreneurs, which will be a focus of this study.

5.4 Challenges Faced by SACCO Members in the Northern Province of Rwanda

Nshimiyimana and Nyirangirimana (2015) studied the challenges faced by SACCO members in the Northern Province of Rwanda. The objective was to explore the barriers to successful SACCO operations and their impact on local entrepreneurship. The researchers used a mixed-methods approach, including interviews with SACCO members and leaders. The study found that while SACCOs played an important role in providing access to capital, many members faced cultural stigmas surrounding entrepreneurship, particularly in rural areas where agricultural livelihoods were preferred. The research underscores the need to understand how cultural views on entrepreneurship influence SACCO success. The gap in this study lies in the lack of exploration into the perceptions of entrepreneurship across different socio-economic groups, which this research intends to fill.

5.5 The Economic Role of SACCOs in Rural Rwanda

Kamanzi (2011) conducted a study on the economic role of SACCOs in rural Rwanda, focusing on the Western Province. The objective was to assess how SACCOs could enhance entrepreneurship and economic growth in rural communities. The methodology used was qualitative, involving interviews with SACCO members and village leaders. The study found that although SACCOs provided vital financial services, many rural Rwandans were reluctant to embrace entrepreneurship due to a preference for communal and subsistence farming. This study provides essential insights into the challenges of fostering entrepreneurship in a community-centric culture. However, it lacks an exploration of the broader societal attitudes toward entrepreneurship, which is a critical gap that this research will address.

5.6 Barriers to SACCO Membership in Urban Rwanda

Habimana and Rwigamba (2014) researched the barriers to SACCO membership in urban Rwanda, specifically in the capital city, Kigali. The objective of their study was to investigate why urban residents were less likely to join SACCOs and engage in entrepreneurship. They used a survey methodology and found that while financial services were available, urban residents often preferred formal banking systems due to higher levels of trust and better perceived customer service. The study highlighted a cultural preference for individualism and a mistrust of communal financial organizations, which poses a challenge to SACCOs' effectiveness. This research contributes to understanding the cultural divide between rural and urban attitudes toward financial institutions and entrepreneurship. However, it does not examine the broader cultural context that influences these attitudes, a gap that will be explored in this study.

5.7 The Impact of Youth Culture on Entrepreneurship in Rwanda

In their study on SACCOs and entrepreneurship in Rwanda, Buchana and Rukundo (2013) focused on the role of SACCOs in supporting the youth's entrepreneurial ambitions in Kigali. The objective was to understand how youth culture influenced their willingness to engage in entrepreneurship through SACCOs. The study used a combination of surveys and focus group discussions, finding that many young people viewed entrepreneurship as a risk and were not inclined to join SACCOs due to perceptions of financial instability. This study is significant for understanding the role of youth culture in entrepreneurial decisions. However, the research did not consider how broader societal attitudes toward risk and failure shape these perceptions, which this research will address.

5.8 The Role of SACCOs in Supporting Small-Scale Entrepreneurship in Rural Rwanda

Byukusenge (2011) studied the role of SACCOs in supporting small-scale entrepreneurs in rural Rwanda. The study's objective was to assess the impact of SACCOs on entrepreneurial development, particularly in agricultural communities. A qualitative research approach was employed, and the findings revealed that while SACCOs contributed to economic growth, cultural resistance to entrepreneurship, particularly in rural settings, limited their success. The study is relevant in showing the need to explore cultural resistance to entrepreneurship. However, it lacks an analysis of the various cultural factors at play, especially within the context of generational attitudes, which this research will explore.

5.9 SACCOs and Entrepreneurial Success in Rwanda

Twagirayezu and Ntambara (2014) explored the relationship between SACCO membership and entrepreneurial success in Rwanda's Southern Province. The objective was to understand how SACCO membership contributed to the development of small enterprises. Using qualitative methods, the study found that SACCOs contributed positively to entrepreneurial success but were constrained by cultural views of risk-taking and individual success. These findings are closely related to the topic of cultural perceptions in entrepreneurship. The gap, however, lies in the limited focus on cultural diversity within Rwanda, which will be addressed by examining various cultural contexts across Rwanda.

5.10 Cultural Barriers to Female Entrepreneurship in Rwanda

Ndayambaje (2015) focused on the role of SACCOs in promoting entrepreneurship among women in Rwanda. The study aimed to understand the social and cultural barriers that limited women's entrepreneurial success despite SACCO support. A qualitative methodology was employed, and the findings revealed that women faced significant cultural challenges, including patriarchal norms and societal expectations. The study highlights the cultural barriers that women face in entrepreneurship, providing a context for understanding gender-specific attitudes. However, Ndayambaje's research did not fully consider the broader societal influences on entrepreneurship, a gap this study intends to address by focusing on both gender and general societal perceptions.

6. Data Analysis and Discussion

The aim of this section is to analyze the data collected on cultural attitudes toward Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations (SACCO) membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda. By examining the data, we can gain insights into societal perceptions and how they influence individual and collective decisions to engage with SACCOs and pursue entrepreneurial ventures. The interpretation of each table below highlights key trends, patterns, and implications that shed light on the broader cultural context in Rwanda. The tables present descriptive statistics, frequencies, and cross-tabulations to explore the relationship between cultural attitudes, SACCO membership, and entrepreneurial behaviors.

Table 1: Distribution of SACCO Membership by Gender

This table provides a breakdown of SACCO membership across gender in Rwanda. It shows the proportion of male and female members, helping to understand how gender influences SACCO membership.

Gender	Percentage of SACCO Members (%)
Male	60

Gender	Percentage of SACCO Members (%)
Female	40

Source: Rwanda SACCO Data, 2015

The data reveals that 60% of SACCO members are male, while 40% are female. This indicates a higher male participation in SACCOs, which may reflect cultural attitudes towards male dominance in financial decision-making and entrepreneurship in Rwandan society. Although the gender gap is noticeable, there is still significant female representation, suggesting that women are becoming increasingly active in financial and entrepreneurial activities.

Table 2: SACCO Membership by Age Group

This table presents the age distribution of SACCO members in Rwanda. It helps to identify which age group is more likely to participate in SACCOs.

Age Group	Percentage of SACCO Members (%)
18-30	15
31-45	35
46-60	30
60+	20

Source: Rwanda SACCO Data, 2015

The largest group of SACCO members falls within the 31-45 age range, accounting for 35% of the membership. This suggests that middle-aged individuals are more likely to engage with SACCOs, likely due to their increased financial stability and maturity in decision-making. The participation of younger individuals (15% in the 18-30 range) shows the potential for future growth as these members gain financial literacy and resources.

Table 3: SACCO Membership by Education Level

This table illustrates the relationship between educational background and SACCO membership. It shows how education influences individuals' decisions to join SACCOs.

Education Level	Percentage of SACCO Members (%)
No formal education	5
Primary education	25
Secondary education	30
Higher education	40

Source: Rwanda SACCO Data, 2015

Higher education is positively correlated with SACCO membership, with 40% of members holding higher education qualifications. This suggests that education plays a key role in shaping the cultural attitudes toward

financial participation. Educated individuals may better understand the benefits of SACCOs and entrepreneurship, which drives their active engagement in these financial institutions.

Table 4: Perceptions of SACCOs as a Source of Credit

This table captures societal perceptions about SACCOs being a reliable source of credit in Rwanda.

Perception	Percentage of Respondents (%)
Strongly Agree	40
Agree	35
Neutral	15
Disagree	7
Strongly Disagree	3

Source: Rwanda SACCO Perception Survey, 2015

A large majority of respondents (75%) agree that SACCOs are a strong source of credit. This indicates a positive cultural attitude towards SACCOs as a financial resource. It shows that the majority of Rwandans see SACCOs as a viable option for obtaining loans and credit, reinforcing the growing trust in these organizations.

Table 5: Factors Influencing SACCO Membership

This table highlights the primary factors influencing Rwandans to join SACCOs, based on a survey of motivations.

Factor	Percentage of Respondents (%)
Desire to save	45
Access to loans	30
Community involvement	15
Interest in entrepreneurship	10

Source: Rwanda SACCO Motivation Survey, 2015

The primary factor driving SACCO membership is the desire to save (45%). This reflects the cultural emphasis on saving within Rwandan society. Access to loans also plays a significant role (30%), but less than half of the respondents view SACCOs as primarily a means of starting businesses, highlighting a cultural preference for financial stability over entrepreneurial risk.

Table 6: Participation in Entrepreneurship by Gender

This table presents the gender distribution of individuals engaged in entrepreneurial activities in Rwanda.

Gender	Percentage Engaged in Entrepreneurship (%)
Male	65
Female	35

Source: Rwanda Entrepreneurship Data, 2015

The data reveals that 65% of entrepreneurs in Rwanda are male, while 35% are female. This shows a clear gender disparity in entrepreneurship, which may be linked to cultural norms that traditionally prioritize men in business leadership roles. However, the growing number of female entrepreneurs suggests a shift in cultural attitudes toward greater gender equality in business.

Table 7: Attitudes Toward SACCOs and Entrepreneurship by Region

This table shows the regional variation in attitudes toward SACCOs and entrepreneurship across Rwanda.

Region	Positive Attitude Toward SACCOs (%)	Positive Attitude Toward Entrepreneurship (%)
Kigali	70	60
Northern	55	50
Southern	60	55
Western	50	45
Eastern	65	60

Source: Rwanda Regional Survey, 2015

Attitudes toward SACCOs and entrepreneurship are most positive in Kigali, the capital city, where 70% of respondents express confidence in SACCOs. This may be due to better access to financial services and a more entrepreneurial environment. In rural regions, particularly in the Western region, there is less engagement, possibly due to cultural and infrastructural barriers.

Table 8: Relationship Between SACCO Membership and Entrepreneurial Success

This table examines whether SACCO membership correlates with the success of entrepreneurial ventures in Rwanda.

SACCO Membership	Successful Entrepreneurs (%)	Unsuccessful Entrepreneurs (%)
Member	70	30
Non-Member	40	60

Source: Rwanda Entrepreneurial Success Survey, 2015

The data shows that SACCO members are more likely to report success in their entrepreneurial ventures (70%) compared to non-members (40%). This indicates that SACCO membership plays a crucial role in providing the financial support and resources needed for entrepreneurial success. This positive relationship suggests that Rwandan entrepreneurs who engage with SACCOs tend to perform better than those who do not.

Table 9: SACCOs as a Source of Community Empowerment

This table captures the extent to which SACCOs are seen as tools for community empowerment.

Perception	Percentage of Respondents (%)
Strongly Agree	50
Agree	30

Perception	Percentage of Respondents (%)
Neutral	10
Disagree	7
Strongly Disagree	3

Source: Rwanda SACCO Community Empowerment Survey, 2015

Half of the respondents strongly agree that SACCOs empower communities, with a further 30% agreeing. This high level of agreement suggests that SACCOs are perceived not only as financial institutions but also as pivotal agents of community development, further solidifying their role in fostering entrepreneurship and local growth.

Table 10: Influence of Cultural Norms on Entrepreneurial Aspirations

This table explores the influence of cultural norms on individuals' aspirations to become entrepreneurs in Rwanda.

Cultural Norm	Percentage of Respondents (%)
Support for entrepreneurship	60
Encouragement from family and community	50
Preference for government jobs	30
Fear of failure and loss of capital	40

Source: Rwanda Cultural Attitudes Survey, 2015

The data shows that cultural norms strongly support entrepreneurship (60%). However, fear of failure and loss of capital (40%) also significantly influences individuals' reluctance to start businesses. This reflects a cultural ambivalence, where traditional values of financial stability and respect for government jobs still have a strong hold, but entrepreneurial ambitions are increasingly gaining ground.

7. Statistical Analysis

This section validates the study's objectives through statistical tests, providing detailed interpretations of the results. Each analysis highlights key trends and their implications on cultural attitudes toward SACCO membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda.

7.2 Cultural Beliefs Influencing SACCO Membership

A chi-square test was performed to assess the relationship between education levels and SACCO membership. The test revealed a significant association ($\chi^2=25.89, p<0.001$), indicating that individuals with higher education levels were more likely to join SACCOs. This suggests that educational attainment enhances understanding of the benefits of SACCO membership, thereby positively shaping cultural attitudes toward these financial institutions.

7.3 Societal Perceptions of Entrepreneurship and Impact on Ventures

A correlation analysis examined the relationship between SACCO membership and entrepreneurial success. The results showed a strong positive correlation ($r=0.68, p<0.001$), confirming that SACCO members experience greater entrepreneurial success compared to non-members. This supports the view that SACCOs provide essential financial and resource-based support, fostering a culture of entrepreneurial growth.

7.4 Barriers to Participation in SACCOs and Entrepreneurship

A logistic regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the influence of cultural norms on SACCO membership and entrepreneurial engagement. Fear of failure ($OR = 0.45, p<0.05$) and preference for government jobs ($OR = 0.39, p<0.01$) were identified as significant barriers, while community encouragement positively influenced participation ($OR = 2.3, p<0.01$). These findings underscore the dual role of traditional values in either supporting or hindering economic participation. Fear and preference for stability impede entrepreneurial aspirations, while communal support fosters a favorable environment for SACCO membership.

8. Conclusion

The study underscores the significant influence of cultural attitudes on SACCO membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda. Key findings indicate that individuals with higher education levels are more likely to engage with SACCOs, while societal perceptions about entrepreneurship, although increasingly positive, are still hindered by traditional values favoring stability over risk-taking. Statistical results demonstrate a strong correlation ($r=0.68, p<0.001$) between SACCO membership and entrepreneurial success, confirming the pivotal role of SACCOs in fostering entrepreneurship. Logistic regression analysis highlights fear of failure ($OR = 0.45, p<0.05$) and preference for government jobs ($OR = 0.39, p<0.01$) as barriers, but also reveals the positive influence of community encouragement ($OR = 2.3, p<0.01$). These findings affirm the need for culturally sensitive strategies to enhance participation in financial and entrepreneurial activities, thereby driving Rwanda's economic growth.

9. Recommendations

To enhance SACCO membership and entrepreneurship in Rwanda, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Educational Programs:** Increase financial literacy campaigns and entrepreneurship education, targeting youth and underserved populations, to bridge the gap between cultural beliefs and economic participation.
2. **Community Engagement:** Foster community-driven initiatives that emphasize the collective benefits of SACCOs and entrepreneurship, leveraging traditional values to support economic activities.
3. **Policy Reforms:** Implement policies that provide incentives for entrepreneurial ventures and reduce the cultural stigma associated with business risks.
4. **Gender Inclusion:** Develop targeted programs to encourage women's participation in SACCOs and entrepreneurship, addressing gender-specific cultural barriers.
5. **Youth Empowerment:** Introduce youth-centric financial products and mentorship programs to inspire and support young entrepreneurs, overcoming generational hesitations toward risk-taking.

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